

end of the season and signify acute moisture stress at the panicle initiation stage of the reproductive phase to the ripening phase of a wet season rice crop.

The possibility of a 3 wk continuous drought is nearly the same throughout the season. An up to 1 wk duration of maximum drought, however, is normally

distributed and is more likely at the intermediate growth stage than at other stages. Extreme drought of 7-wk duration is rare. □

Farming systems

Fish output effects on rice yield in a rice-fish farming system in Luzhou Region, China

Xu Fuxian and Tan Zhenbo, Rice Research Institute, Sichuan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Luzhou 646000, China

The percentage of rice yield increase (PRYI) went from -11.7 to 8.1 and fish output from 0.3 to 2.25 t/ha in 13.1 ha in Luzhou in 1987. The PRYI was negatively and significantly correlated with fish output, where $y = 11.5529 - 10.3368x$, $n = 9$, and $r = -0.9951^{**}$. We conducted studies in 1988-89 to learn why rice yields decreased with a large fish output in a rice-fish farming system.

We planted hybrid rice Shanyou 63 in a 20- × 13-m plot in a randomized block design. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. A cross furrow, 0.5 m deep and 0.4 m wide, was made. Its area represented 10% of that of the plot. Fish fry, each weighing 50 g, were released at a ratio of 3 carp:5 grass carp:2 crucian carp.

We transplanted rice seedlings in mid-April at 1 seedling/hill, spaced 26 × 13 cm. Maximum tillering occurred before June, and the crop matured in mid-August. June to August is the best time for fish growth in Luzhou. In the low fish output system, fish fry were released in mid-June and harvested in October. Tillering was not inhibited, because at the 2- to 3-cm water depth, fish loosen the soil and control weeds and insect pests while feeding. Incorporating fish in ricefields increased 1,000-grain weight, spikelets per panicle, and seed setting percentage (see table).

In a rice-fish farming system with large fish output, fry must be released in April to fully utilize light and temperature resources during fish growth. Irrigated ricefields with water depth of 15 cm inhibited tiller production and decreased productive panicles. This decreased grain yield but

Effect of fish output on grain yield in rice-fish farming system.

Treatment	Seedlings transplanted (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Productive panicles (no./m ²)	Seed set (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Fry (no./m ²)	Fish wt increase (g/fry per d)	Fish output (t/ha)
<i>1988</i>								
Rice-fish	52	383	270	89.6	7.6	0.5	1.5	1.6
Rice alone	52	545	351	86.6	8.8	—	—	—
Rice-fish	28	470	274	89.4	8.3	0.3	1.3	0.9
Rice alone	28	521	287	87.1	7.8	—	—	—
<i>1989</i>								
Rice-fish	51	390	274	76.8	6.6	0.5	2.4	2.1
Rice alone	51	555	338	74.9	7.2	—	—	—
Rice-fish	28	428	278	78.3	8.7	0.3	1.4	0.7
Rice alone	28	454	282	76.3	8.1	—	—	—

increased 1,000-grain weight, spikelets per panicle, and percentage of seed setting (see table).

Farmers should increase the number of transplanted seedlings, adopt rice

ridge culture for deeper water depth, and use rice varieties with high tillering ability to increase grain yield in rice-fish farming systems with large fish output. □

Farm machinery

The peristaltic pump: a promising, stream-driven, water-lifting device for agriculture

L. C. A. Naegel, M. C. Pasikatan, and G. R. Quick, IRRI

Many farms in developing countries are predominantly rainfed. The availability of water during the dry season is a major constraint on agricultural productivity. Stream-driven pumps could make fields located above fast-flowing rivers or canals more productive.

We have developed and tested two pumps that make use of locally available materials: a spiral pump and a peristaltic pump.

Peristaltic pumps work on the simple principle of rollers rotating inside a stationary housing and pressing one or more elastomeric tubes against a cylindrical

housing wall. The rotation of the rollers alternately compresses and releases the tubing. After compression, the tubing recovers its original shape and creates a vacuum, which makes the pump self-priming (see figure).

The prototype uses the brake drum of a truck (30 cm inner diam) and the plate of a disk brake. Two types of 2.5-cm tubing were tested: an expensive imported neoprene and a cheap, locally available polyester-reinforced chemical hose.

The pump was installed above a water-filled drum and connected through a chain drive to a 1-hp, variable-speed electric motor. Tests under laboratory conditions used a varying number of rollers (2, 3, and 4) at different speeds of rotation (24, 36, 51, 62, 73 RPM), different clearances between the rollers and the brake drum (7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 mm), and different total static heads (0.4, 5.32, 8.42, and 10.53 m). Power requirements, flow rate, and